

ZnS based Core shell Quantum Dots for next generation Bio-imaging

B. Manikanta^a, Neeli Chandran ^a, J. Prajit^b, Swapna S. Nair^{*a}, Rajendra P^{*b}

^aDepartment of Physics, Central University of Kerala, Kasaragod, Kerala 671314

^bDepartment of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Central University of Kerala, Kasaragod, Kerala,
671314

*Corresponding author Email id: swapna.s.nair@gmail.com, Mobile number: 8281261375

*Corresponding author Email id: praj74@gmail.com, Mobile number: 9061877113

Abstract

ZnS is a wide band gap semiconductor and it shows remarkable properties that can be exploited for versatile applications including transistors, LEDs, biology and medicine etc. ZnS based core shell nanoparticles is prepared by co-precipitation technique with edible dye as the shell. The absorption and PL measurements shows their absorption maximum at 499 nm. The nano particles are incubated in Hela cells and monitored cellular uptake and fluorescence.

Fluorescence image of Hela Cell

Keywords: ZnS Nanoparticles, Surface Plasmon Resonance, Hela

References

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